

Introduction

The statement that data is of grave importance to organisations and that effective usage can yield large advantages is far from new and, hence, recognised widely. Following this, the amount of data collected and utilised by organisations is ever-growing. This ongoing trend has emphasised the need for proper management and governance of data, as is further recognised by a growing number of organisations that are formally incorporating data governance structures into the organisation.

Popular among these data governance structures is the usage of data ownership models. A data ownership model, or ownership model, is an organisational model that serves to coordinate data management, maintenance and usage. An example of such a model can be seen in the figure below, based on van Gils (2020) ¹.

Example of a data ownership model (taken from van Gils (2020) ¹).

A data ownership model uses the assignment of roles to people within the organisation as a basis for coordinative actions. Roles that are generally though not exclusively found are 'Data Owners', 'Data Stewards' and 'Data Users'. The fulfillers of these roles, in turn, have certain accountabilities, responsibilities and activities within the organisation's data management/governance capability (van Gils, 2020). If formalised, this role-based model generally depicts lines connecting the different roles to indicate the primary interaction between agents while fulfilling their roles, as seen in the figure.

While organisations are increasingly incorporating data governance structures, like data ownership models, only few practical tools are readily available for data management professionals and organisations to be used during the design and implementation of such data ownership models. Against this background, a practical tool called 'Ownership Model Implementation Tool' (OMIT) was developed to better enable organisations in designing and implementing a data ownership model.

¹ van Gils, B. (2020). *Data Management: A gentle introduction: Balancing theory and practice*. Van Haren.

What is the intended use of the OMIT?

The OMIT is a practical tool to be used during the design, implementation and (further) improvement of an organisational data ownership model. The OMIT aims to:

- 1) Enable organisations to reflect on the current state of data ownership model practices
- 2) Provide guidance in establishing a 'roadmap' or list with areas for improvement that aim to work towards an intended future state of data ownership model practices
- 3) Ensure that crucial data ownership model dimensions and aspects have been considered and addressed appropriately

The OMIT consists of 7 crucial dimensions, shown in the table below, that need to be considered by organisations when addressing their data ownership model. Each dimension has a certain amount of questions that allow self-assessment of the organisation along the crucial data ownership model dimensions.

Central ownership model dimensions in the OMIT	
1. Data Quality and Integrity	2. Confidentiality and Security
3. Risk and Compliance	4. Data Access and Usage
5. People and Culture	6. Ownership Model Design Choices
7. Prerequisites	

Who is the OMIT intended for?

The OMIT is targeting data management professionals that aim to fulfil one or more of the aforementioned objectives. These may be data management professionals internal to an organisation or external professionals, like consultants who are helping an organisation in establishing a data ownership model. Depending on the size of the organisation, these professionals are likely situated within or are often consulting with the higher hierarchical levels of the organisation. Professionals using the OMIT are expected to have multiple years of experience in data management/governance.

Likely, the necessary knowledge to make a full assessment with the OMIT is dispersed across the organisation, depending on the size of the organisation. As such, using the OMIT likely requires the involvement and collaboration of multiple stakeholders from various departments.

How to use the OMIT

The questions within each of the 7 dimensions are consciously formulated in a rather broad manner. The aim of this is to provoke a broad thought process regarding the content of the questions, aiming to yield an overview as complete as possible. Answers will therefore be qualitative and will be extensive in size. This implies that answering the questions should be done as detailed and complete as possible. This potentially takes a considerable amount of time and, as was mentioned before, will likely require the collaboration of multiple stakeholders within the organisation.

Answers that have been formulated can, later on, serve as a benchmark for establishing what data ownership model aspects are areas for improvement. This should help to formulate what topics an organisation can/should address to achieve an intended future state for data ownership model practices.

Instructions and additional advice

- Users are advised to browse through the entire tool upfront as some of the latter questions relate to earlier questions.
- Users may encounter difficulties while answering certain questions due to a lacking presence of certain topics within the organisation. This is a direct result of the consciously broad formulation of questions within the OMIT. Users should bear in mind that the topics within questions are also meant to provoke broad thinking and are meant to provide guidance in establishing areas for improvement. If specific topics or aspects are not or are only very limitedly present, this could indicate a potential area for improvement.
- If the user finds this suitable, the OMIT questions can easily be transformed to allow a Likert-scale answer. This implies that questions are not qualitatively answered but are instead scored on a scale of 1 to 5 indicating the level of presence of an aspect within the organisation. For questions to be answerable in this manner, slight reformulations are necessary ².

Consider question 1.8 as an example. First, the question should be pulled apart: *“Are metrics/KPIs or standards being utilised to measure data quality?”*, *“To what extent are these metrics/KPIs formalised?”* and *“To what extent are these measures objective?”*.

Second, the question should be reformulated so that the most appropriate answering option can then be filled in, like *“Metrics/KPIs are ... utilised to measure data quality.* Considering the following examples of possible Likert-scale answer options, questions could then be answered as follows:

	Possible Likert-scale measures ²				
Option 1	very low/none	low	Average	High	Very high
Option 2	very little/none	little	Average	Much	Very much
Option 3	(almost) never	sometimes	Occasionally	Usually	(almost) always

Here the answer ‘never’ implies the lowest level (1) and the answer ‘always’ implies the highest level (5). Scores of individual questions can then be aggregated and averaged per dimension to yield a maturity level per dimension. By doing so, organisations might find it easier to establish a concrete maturity level of current data ownership model practices to be used as a point of reference now and in further development of the data ownership model.

- Users are advised to use the OMIT in conjunction with other practical (assessment) tools, like data governance maturity tools, to enhance the holisticness of the resulting data ownership model.
- There is a plethora of different terminologies and wording when it comes to data governance and data ownership model practices. To partially address this, definitions have been provided for each dimension to ensure users are aware of the implied semantics in the OMIT. However, users should be aware that while utilising the OMIT in conjunction with other practical tools, terminology and/or wording may differ and should be regarded with care.

² For inspiration on how to re-formulate questions and what Likert-scale measures to use, users may find Marchildon et al. (2018) useful, via Marchildon, P., Bourdeau, S., Hadaya, P., & Labissière, A. (2018). Data governance maturity assessment tool: A design science approach. *Projectics/Proyèctica/Projectique*, (2), 155-193.

Ownership Model Implementation Tool (OMIT)

1st Dimension - Data Quality and Integrity
<p>In this dimension, Data Quality concerns those methods and practices undertaken by the organisation to ensure all data meets certain quality standards, based on predefined requirements and data quality dimensions (for a clarification of data quality dimensions, please refer to ³).</p> <p>In this dimension, Data Integrity concerns the organisational efforts in ensuring accurate and consistent data that can be placed into context, the latter indicating the importance of metadata. By all data, we mean data from all sources and in all content formats.</p>
<p>Question 1.1a To what extent have data quality dimensions been established that are essential for the organisation? (for a clarification of data quality dimensions, please refer to ³).</p>
<p>Question 1.1b To what extent are data quality dimensions and targeted data quality levels tailored to fit specific situations in which data is needed?</p>
<p>Question 1.2 To what extent and in what way has (essential) data been classified to support data quality management and how does this current state of data classification influence data quality issues?</p>
<p>Question 1.3 What datasets and source systems/golden sources are crucial for the organisation's core business and management information and to what extent do these exhibit data quality issues?</p>
<p>Question 1.4 Are data quality issues documented and to what extent are they used as inputs for solutions?</p>
<p>Question 1.5 What (technical and operational) processes and measures are currently in place to address and improve data quality and to what extent are these processes formalised?</p>
<p>Question 1.6 To what extent is data/business modelling deployed (i.e. establishing a conceptual model with definitions and interrelationships) and has a data glossary, catalogue or dictionary been made?</p>
<p>Question 1.7 To what extent is reference data being utilised and to what extent is this reference data being maintained and actualised in an organised manner?</p>
<p>Question 1.8 What policies are currently in place to address and improve data quality and to what extent are these policies formalised?</p>
<p>Question 1.9 What metrics/KPIs or standards are being utilised to measure data quality, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent are these measures objective?</p>

³ Users may find the DAMA NL Dimensions of Data Quality (Van Nederpelt & Black, 2020; Werkgroep Data Kwaliteit DAMA NL, 2023) useful for clarification and may utilise these for guidance in establishing data quality dimensions, via <https://dama-nl.org/dimensions-of-data-quality-en/>

2nd Dimension - Confidentiality and Security

The **Confidentiality and Security** dimension refers to those methods and practices undertaken by the organisation to ensure sensitive data is kept secure and confidential, including privacy-related practices. It concerns both technical and non-technical methods and practices to ensure sensitive data is secure and shielded from unintended parties.

Question 2.1a

What domains, datasets, data sources and systems require the most extensive confidentiality and security measures?

Question 2.1b

To what extent can the confidentiality and security of data within these domains, datasets, data sources and systems be guaranteed?

Question 2.2

To what extent and in what way has (essential) data been classified to support confidentiality and security measures and in what way does the current state of data classification influence confidentiality and security-related issues?

Question 2.3

What is your assessment of the frequency and severity of data breaches, are data breaches documented and to what extent are they being used as inputs for preventive solutions?

Question 2.4

To what extent are authorisations provided based on (formal) policies and to what extent are authorisations frequently actualised?

Question 2.5

To what extent are methods and/or measures deployed to shield sensitive data from unauthorised parties?

Concrete examples of methods to shield sensitive data from unauthorised parties are encryption, firewalls, multifactor authentication, physical security measures and so forth. Examples of industry standards within the confidentiality and security domain potentially relevant to establish these methods and/or measures are versions of the NIST 800-standards and ISO/IEC 27001.

Question 2.6

To what extent are only specific parts of datasets and/or records designated to be subject to confidentiality and security measures, considering both primary- and secondary-used data?

Question 2.7

What policies and/or standards are currently in place to ensure adequate confidentiality and security measures are taken, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent have both primary- and secondary-used data been considered?

It should be clear that organisational policies and standards are different from the aforementioned industry standards (i.e. NIST 800 and ISO/IEC 27001), even though these industry standards can potentially serve as a foundation for organisational policies and standards.

Question 2.8

What (technical) processes are currently in place to ensure the necessary confidentiality and security standards are met, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent have both primary- and secondary-used data been considered?

3rd Dimension - Risk and Compliance

In this dimension, **Risk** refers to the methods and processes by which data-related risks are identified, qualified, quantified, rejected, accepted, and/or mitigated in an organisation. These methods and processes do not only concern data security risks but also concern broader organisational risks for which adequate data management is of central importance.

An example of such a broad organisational risk that is still data management related could be financial risks that are identified, prevented and/or caused by inaccurate data and, therefore potentially, inadequate data management.

In this dimension, **Compliance** refers to the efforts of an organisation, concerning its data management/governance, to ensure relevant legislation is complied with.

Question 3.1

What, if any, legislation is of central importance to the organisation and its core business and to what extent can compliance be guaranteed based on data management practices?

Question 3.2

To what extent and in what way has (essential) data been classified to support risk and compliance measures and in what way does the current state of data classification influence risk and compliance-related issues?

Question 3.3

To what extent are data management practices aligned with overall organisational risk management and to what extent do data management practices reinforce overall organisational risk management?

Question 3.4

To what extent are (security) risk assessments conducted within the data management domain and to what extent do these risk assessments determine the undertaken pre-emptive measures?

Question 3.5

What (technical) processes are currently in place to ensure compliance with legislation and to enhance risk management and to what extent are these formalised?

Question 3.6

What policies are currently in place to ensure compliance with legislation and sound risk management and to what extent are these formalised?

Question 3.7

To what extent have the potential effects for data management practices of changes in legislation been anticipated pre-emptively?

4th Dimension - Data Access and Usage

In this dimension, **Data Access** concerns those methods, practices, systems and processes within the organisation that arrange and coordinate the access to certain desired data. This includes both the user's and supplier's side of gaining and facilitating access to the desired data. In this dimension, **Data Usage** concerns those methods, practices and processes within the organisation that serve to coordinate the usage of data by data recipients/users.

Question 4.1a

Is there a formalised process in place for facilitating data access for both internal and external stakeholders?

What is meant here, is the entire process from the moment a potential user of data takes action to be able to use the data until the moment that user starts using the data. This includes potential intermediary processes of data preparation and making it available/forwarding it.

Question 4.1b

To what extent does this process meet confidentiality & security and risk & compliance standards?

Question 4.1c

To what extent is the route of the data through this process and the mutations along the way traceable and to what extent is this process transparent for others?

Question 4.1d

Related to question 4.1c, to what extent does this process consider traceability and transparency of secondary-used data?

Question 4.2

Is there a dedicated system for internal and external data sharing and to what extent can this system guarantee confidentiality & security and risk & compliance standards are met?

Question 4.3

To what extent and in what way has (essential) data been classified to support the process of data access and usage and in what way does the current state of data classification influence related issues?

Question 4.4

To what extent is the current state of requesting data, providing/obtaining it and subsequently using it deemed satisfactory by all stakeholders involved? (i.e. how does it currently 'perform'?)

Question 4.5a

Are data sharing agreements (DSAs) made as a means to guide the reciprocal relationship between data recipients and providers and to what extent are these DSAs formalised?

Question 4.5b

To what extent is the current way of working with DSAs deemed satisfactory by all stakeholders involved and what is your assessment of how well this way of working currently performs?

'Way of working with DSAs', implies everything related to the process of creating, logging and enacting the DSAs as well as the content, form and format of the DSAs.

5th Dimension - People and Culture

The **People and Culture** dimension concerns human factors and organisational culture, the latter mostly determined by human factors, related to the organisation's data management practices.

This dimension mostly aims to establish how the organisation generally values data and its management/governance and how the organisation approaches 'managing people'.

Question 5.1

What is your assessment of the 'data literacy' throughout the entire organisation?

Data literacy means the overall capability to understand and work with, communicate about and argue based on data (Gartner, 2021⁴). For example, a data literate person (not working within data management) can read and understand a common table, communicate about it with peers and also argue based on it. This essentially implies the capacity of turning data into information.

Question 5.2

What is your assessment of the awareness of the importance of data, data quality and data management throughout the entire organisation? (e.g. from operational to executive level)

Question 5.3

To what extent is there a conscious approach or management style for data management practices that affect people within the organisation? (e.g. bottom-up vs. top-down, collaborative vs. directive, command & control vs. non-invasive)

'A conscious approach' implies that the organisation's culture and the current and intended future data management/governance maturity level have been considered.

Question 5.4

To what extent is there a conscious approach when functions or roles need to be filled? (e.g. searching for intrinsically motivated role-fulfillers vs. assigning roles)

Roles and/or functions that are generally found in a data ownership model were mentioned in the introduction. Examples are Data Owner, Data Steward, Data User, Data Custodian and any of the above combined with a title such as executive, chief, technical, business, coordinating and so on. The specific name of the roles or functions, however, often differs widely per organisation.

'A conscious approach' implies that the organisation's culture and the current and intended future data management/governance maturity level have been considered.

Question 5.5a

What metrics/KPIs are being utilised to manage people, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent are these measures objective?

Question 5.5b

To what extent are these metrics/KPIs designed and used to facilitate the personal and functional development of people?

Question 5.6

What processes and/or policies are in place to enhance the popularity of data management practices and to support data enthusiasts and to what extent are these formalised?

⁴ Gartner. (2021, August). *A Data and Analytics Leader's Guide to Data Literacy*. Retrieved January 10, 2023, from <https://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/a-data-and-analytics-leaders-guide-to-data-literacy>

6th Dimension - Data Ownership Model Design Choices

The **Data Ownership Model Design Choices** dimension concerns the designing of the data ownership model as a formal organisational model that serves to coordinate data management, maintenance and usage (refer to the introduction for a clarification of 'data ownership model'). The questions below address the central design choices when developing, implementing and/or improving a data ownership model and aim to guide organisations in doing so.

Question 6.1

To what extent has a data ownership model been designed and implemented and to what extent is this model formalised?

Use the current state of the data ownership model as a foundation to further build upon during the following questions.

Question 6.2

To what extent has a conscious design choice been made regarding the scope of the data ownership model? (e.g. according to subject area, business domain, applications/systems, business processes, etc. (Polsky, 2013⁵; van Gils, 2020¹)).

Question 6.3

Your assessment of all prior questions should indicate what central data ownership model accountabilities, responsibilities and activities are currently present, which are not and to what extent they are formalised.

To what extent has secondary usage of data been considered in establishing these accountabilities and responsibilities, in establishing who is/remains accountable/responsible as data moves through the organisation and to what extent has this been formalised?

Question 6.4

Based on the assessment of all prior questions, to what extent are the central data ownership model accountabilities, responsibilities and activities already being fulfilled by employees and to what extent are the roles and/or functions these employees fulfil formalised? ⁶

Question 6.5

Based on your assessment of all prior questions, what data ownership model roles or functions are not yet present and are deemed necessary to fulfil the established central accountabilities, responsibilities and activities?

Please refer to the introduction and question 5.4 for an example of possible functions and/or roles.

⁵ Polsky, A. (2013). *Data stewardship on the ground, notes from the field* [Presentation at the Data Governance Conference in London].

⁶ Users may utilise RACI or RASCI-matrices as a tool to divide and visualise the distribution of accountabilities, responsibilities and activities among the different roles and/or functions.

Question 6.6a

Is there a decision-making body involved in data management/governance decision-making that includes representatives from across the entire organisation?

Question 6.6b

To what extent has this decision-making body been formalised?

Question 6.7a

To what extent is it clear for employees in data ownership model roles and/or functions what the accountabilities, responsibilities and activities are for each respective role and/or function? (i.e. is it clear to them what can be expected and demanded from each other?)

Question 6.7b

To what extent has the former been formalised?

7th Dimension - Prerequisites

The *Prerequisites* dimension refers to factors or conditions that need to be met, at least to some extent, for data ownership model implementations to succeed.

This implies that data ownership model implementations can still succeed when one or more prerequisites have not or have only partially been met. However, not meeting these prerequisites gravely lowers the chance for successful data ownership model implementations.

Question 7.1a

What is your assessment of the executive-level endorsement of data management/governance practices and is data generally seen as an asset by executives?

Question 7.1b

To what extent does the executive-level endorsement of data management/governance practices resonate in their decisions/actions and in providing mandate for decisions/actions?

Question 7.1c

What is your assessment of the operational-level endorsement of data-related practices and is data generally seen as important at the operational level?

Question 7.2

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent does the current state and intended future state of the data ownership model guarantee executive- and operational-level endorsement of data management/governance practices?

Question 7.3

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent is the current state and intended future state of the data ownership model in line with the organisation's strategy, vision and general (non-data related) policies?

Question 7.4

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent is the current state and intended future state of the data ownership model in line with the overall Data Management Framework and/or Data Governance Framework?

Question 7.5

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent do the current state and intended future state of the data ownership model guarantee the cultivation of a data culture within

A 'data culture' can be described as the collective beliefs and behaviours of people in an organisation that enable leveraging data as an organisational asset (Southehal, 2022 ⁷). This involves those beliefs and behaviours that reinforce the organisational data literacy and overall endorsement of data management/governance throughout the entire organisation.

(Format, layout and formulation of definitions based on Marchildon et al. (2018 ²))

⁷ Southehal, P. (2022, June). *Data Culture: What It Is And How To Make It Work*. Retrieved March 28, 2023, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2022/06/27/data-culture-what-it-is-and-how-to-make-it-work/>